

1 Relationship between bound water and reserve carbohydrates associated with cellular integrity in
2 *Fragaria vesca* under different storage conditions.

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34 16 **Abstract**

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37 17 It has been recognized that beneficial high CO₂ delays wilting and reduces weight loss in harvested plant
38 18 products. Since strawberry fruits have high tolerance thresholds to CO₂, it is of interest to know what
39 19 changes occur in fruit water status when these thresholds are reached and exceeded. Changes in the content
40 20 of bound water were analysed in relation to the simple sugars, polyols and fructooligosaccharides (FOS) in
41 21 Mara des Bois strawberries (*Fragaria vesca* L.) stored at severe low temperature (0 °C) with 0, 20 or 40 %
42 22 CO₂. The relationship between cellular water status and these compounds was analyzed at the end of a 3
43 23 day treatments and after exposure to air for one day. Unfavourable storage conditions were associated with
44 24 a significant decrease in the levels of bound water, and in simple sugars, 1-kestose and *myo*-inositol. The
45 25 1-kestose and *myo*-inositol content was enhanced when fruit treated with excessive high CO₂ (40 %) were
46 26 **exposed** to air at the same time as there was a marked increase in bound water
47 27 content and a restoration of intracellular water. The ability of fruit to modulate the accumulation of these
48 28 compounds, and by extension the water binding strength, in conjunction with the pool of the bound water

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fraction, appears to be an important mechanism associated with structural cellular integrity. Variations in the percentages of air space and weight loss produced by enhancing the CO₂ treatments during storage at 0 °C were also analyzed.

Keywords: strawberry; high CO₂; fructooligosaccharides; bound water; air space; *myo*-inositol.

Introduction

Water is the most abundant molecule in fruit, and it has a high impact on its quality and storability, especially in strawberries. The fact that only about 10 % of the solid matter in strawberries has to support a large amount of liquid could explain, in part, their high perishability and susceptibility to textural damage, fungal decay and liquid leakage. Moreover, changes in fruit water status are involved in the regulation of ripening processes (Frenkel and Hartman, 2012) and modifications in the content of the different water fractions have been reported (Goñi et al. 2007). Changes in the bound water fraction are at least partially the result of modifications in the levels of hydrophilic molecules with high water-binding capacity. It was reported that the bound water that represents unfreezable water (Wolfe et al. 2002) plays an important role in tolerance to different environmental stresses such as freezing and drought (Rascio et al. 1998; Sun 2000). Indeed, fruit stored at low temperature under adequate high CO₂ treatment had a larger bound water fraction (Goñi et al. 2011), in association with an increase of inulin series fructans (Blanch et al. 2011). Fructans have been increasingly recognized as protective agents in stress environments (Valluru and Van den Ende 2008). In addition to their protective influence on cell structures, fructooligosaccharides (FOS), which consist of linear β (2-1) linked fructose residues with a terminal glucose residue, participate in carbon storage. Consequently, variations in the levels of sucrose, glucose and fructose are thought to be linked to the changes in FOS. Sugar alcohols, or polyols, are also closely associated with hexose metabolism, and they act as compatible solutes in response to salt and drought stress and play multiple roles in plant protection (Williamson et al. 2002; Merchant and Richter 2011). However, the mechanism by which polyhydroxyalcohols could protect fruits under changing environmental conditions is less well understood.

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It has long been recognized that beneficial CO₂ delays wilting (Smith et al. 1966), reduces water loss and incidence of decay in highly perishable fruits (El-Kazzaz et al. 1983; Pretel et al. 2006; Sanchez-Ballesta et al. 2006). However, when the CO₂ concentrations are above the toleration threshold they can also be harmful. Development of off-flavours is a well-known common detrimental effect caused by fermentative metabolite accumulation, especially when high CO₂ concentrations are combined with reduced oxygen levels. Therefore, it would be useful to identify the outstanding metabolic markers indicative of fruit damage associated with excessive CO₂ levels.

Furthermore, by taking advantage of *Fragaria vesca* tolerance to high CO₂ levels, benefits can be obtained if the detrimental effect can be mitigated after transfer to ambient CO₂. Moreover, since commercial harvests last several days, which implies that strawberries are picked from different inflorescences, benefits might be greatly enhanced if effective high CO₂ treatment can be applied to different harvested strawberries produced by different inflorescences.

The aim of the present work was to analyze how changes in bound water fractions were correlated with reserve carbohydrates and cellular structure in strawberry fruit stored under different storage conditions. For this purpose, Mara des Bois strawberries (*Fragaria vesca* L.) from various inflorescences were stored at low temperature (0 °C) and treated with increased CO₂ concentrations (0, 20 and 40 %). The amount of bound water fraction, simple sugars, short-chain FOS and polyols were analyzed at the end of CO₂ treatments and when strawberries were transferred to air for one additional day. The ability of polyols (mannitol, sorbitol and *myo*-inositol) to modify water behaviour, and the contribution of high CO₂ treatments to weight loss, air space and cellular tissue integrity were also determined.

2. Materials and methods

Plant material

The organic strawberries used in this study (*Fragaria vesca* L. cv. Mara des Bois) were grown in an orchard in San Sebastian de los Reyes (Madrid, Spain) whose coordinates are 40° 32' 49" N, 3° 37' 33" W. Strawberries belonging to various inflorescences were harvested, immediately transported to the Institute of Food Science Technology and Nutrition and selected for uniform size and colour. The strawberries with 8.9 % total soluble solids as °Brix, 0.7 % titratable acidity, and an external *L**18, *a**38, *b**28 colour were stored at 0 °C (±0.5) and >95 % RH in three sealed 1 m³ containers. Fifteen plastic boxes containing approximately 0.5 kg of strawberries per box were treated for

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86 3 days with increasing amounts of CO₂ (0, 20 and 40 %, balanced with 20 % O₂ and made up to 100 %
87 with N₂). Initially, at the end of the 3 day sampling period and 1 day after exposure to air, 45 strawberries
88 were assessed for quality, and another 45 were removed at random from each of the treatment groups and
89 divided into three batches of 15 berries. The 15 strawberries from each batch were used as **biological**
90 **replicates**. Each replicate was mixed, frozen in liquid nitrogen and stored at -80 °C for further analysis.

91 92 *Extraction and chromatographic determination of glucose, fructose, sucrose and polyols*

93 Berry samples of approximately 3 g were homogenized in 5 mL of ultra-pure water, centrifuged at 30,000
94 g for 20 min and the supernatants were filtered through a 0.45 µm pore size membrane. Sugars and polyols
95 were determined by HPAEC-PAD with a Metrosep Carb 1–250 IC column (4.6 mm × 250 mm). Samples
96 were analyzed on an Ion Chromatography 817 Bioscan (Metrohm, Herisau, Switzerland) system equipped
97 with a pulsed amperometric detector (PAD) and a gold electrode. Isocratic elution was carried out with 10
98 mL/L NaOH 40 % w/w. Samples (1.5 mL) were injected using an autosampler (model, 838 Advanced
99 Sample Processor, Metrohm, Herisau, Switzerland) and the flow rate through the column was 1 mL/min,
100 leading to a sampling time (ts) of 38 min. Appropriate dilutions of solutions containing glucose, fructose,
101 sucrose, *myo*-inositol, D-sorbitol and D-mannitol (Sigma, Steinheim, Germany) were used as calibration
102 standards. Chromatographic peaks were identified by comparing sample retention times with those of
103 known standard mixtures. The content of these sugars was expressed in mg/g fresh weight (FW) of the
104 sample and the content of these polyols was expressed in µg/g FW. The data were expressed as the mean
105 of three analyses of two different biological **replicates**. The data were acquired using DataApex Clarity
106 software.

107 *Extraction and chromatographic determination of FOS*

108 The quantification of nystose, kestopentaose, and that of 1-kestose (which required pre-treatment with an
109 activated carbon Darco G60, 100 mesh (Sigma, Steinheim, Germany) to remove the mono- and
110 disaccharides), was determined according to the method of Blanch et al. (2011). Briefly, the samples were
111 extracted with 85 % ethanol, boiled under reflux and centrifuged at 5,000 g for 20 min at 4 °C. The
112 supernatant was evaporated and redissolved in deionised water, filtered through 0.22 µm filters and
113 analysed by HPAEC-PAD using a CarboPac PA1 carbohydrate column. A three-step PAD protocol was
114 employed and the samples (1.5 mL) were injected using an autosampler (model, 838 Advanced Sample
115 Processor, Metrohm, Herisau, Switzerland). FOS identification was performed by comparing the retention

116 time of standard mixtures 1-kestose and nystose from Sigma (Steinheim, Germany) and kestopentaose
117 from Megazyme (Co. Wicklow, Ireland) and the FOS content was expressed in µg/g FW of the sample.

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119 *Determination of water status and water distribution*

120 The unfreezable (bound) water fraction and freezing point were determined using DSC, according to the
121 method of Goñi et al. (2011). The heat flow curves for freezing points (T_f , °C) were determined in
122 triplicate using a DSC822e apparatus (Mettler-Toledo Inc., Columbus, OH, USA). Samples were placed
123 in sealed aluminium pans that were cooled to -80 °C at 10 °C/min, and they were scanned from -80 to 25
124 °C at a rate of 10 °C/min. The resulting thermograms were evaluated paying particular attention to the onset
125 temperature and the enthalpy of the melting endotherm from which the quantities of bound water was
126 calculated. The freezing point was considered as the intersection of the tangent and baseline of the left side
127 of the melting peak.

128 Microstructure analysis was performed using low temperature scanning electron microscopy (LT-SEM),
129 using a Zeiss DSN- 960 electron scanning microscope equipped with a cold stage (Cryostrans CT-1500,
130 Oxford Instruments, Oxford, UK). Frozen tissue sections were cryofractured at -180 °C, etched at -90 °C,
131 gold-coated and subsequently transferred to the microscope where they were analyzed at -150 to -160 °C.
132 Samples were observed with both secondary and retro-dispersed electrons, and the best images were selected
133 in each case.

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135 *Determination of the percentages of air space and weight loss*

136 The percentage of air space was calculated from the ratio of the fruit density and the density of the juice,
137 according to the equation:

$$\text{air space (\%)} = 100 \frac{V_a}{V_F} = 100 \left(1 - \frac{\rho_F}{\rho_J}\right)$$

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139 where

$$\rho_F = \frac{M_F}{V_F}$$

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141 and

58 116 time of standard mixtures 1-kestose and nystose from Sigma (Steinheim, Germany) and kestopentaose
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$$p_j = \frac{M_j}{V_j} = \frac{M_F}{V_F - V_I}$$

60 117 from Megazyme (Co. Wicklow, Ireland) and the FOS content was expressed in $\mu\text{g/g}$ FW of the sample.
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65 119 *Determination of water status and water distribution*
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143 (ρ_F) is fruit density, (ρ_J) is juice density, M_F is fruit mass, V_F is fruit volume, M_J is juice
144 volume, and V_a is air volume.

145 The density of six individual fruits was measured using a balance with 1 mg sensitivity by placing the
146 whole fruit in a pre-tarred steel mesh fully immersed in a glass container with ethanol. Ethanol **instead of**
147 **water** was used to avoid the tendency of water to invade the air spaces when the fruit is immersed.

148 The fresh weight of the fruit was determined gravimetrically and weight loss was expressed as the
149 percentage of the initial weight.

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151 *Determination of the amount of unfrozen water of the different polyols*

152 The anti-freeze characteristics of the different polyols were evaluated calorimetrically through the amount
153 of unfrozen water (U_w) defined as described by Furuki (2002) on a DSC822e (Mettler-Toledo Inc.,
154 Columbus, OH, USA), with slight differences. Aqueous solutions of polyol at the desired concentrations
155 were prepared by weighing with deionized distilled water. The polyol concentration was gradually changed
156 from 5 weight % up to a maximum of 50 weight %. A series of prepared aqueous solutions were sealed in
157 independent vials and kept for 24 h at 25 °C in an incubator to allow them to reach steady state. Aqueous
158 samples (5-10 μ L) were placed in 40 μ L hermetically sealed aluminium pans and cooled from 25 °C to -
159 80 °C at a rate of 10 °C/min. The samples were left at this temperature for 5 min and then heated to 25 °C
160 at 10 °C/min. **The heating scan was used to determine the latent heat of the melting ice (ΔH_m) by integration**
161 **of the melting endotherm and the T_g ' by the deflection midpoint in the heat flow versus temperature curve.**
162 U_w was determined by extrapolating ΔH_m to zero, which was linearly dependent on the polyol concentration
163 (weight %) as expressed below:

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$$U_w = \frac{100 - C'_s}{\frac{M_r(H_2O)}{C'_s} M_r(\text{polyol})}$$

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where (ρ_F) is fruit density, (ρ_J) is juice density, M_F is fruit mass, V_F is fruit volume, M_J is juice volume, and V_a is air volume.

The density of six individual fruits was measured using a balance with 1 mg sensitivity by placing the whole fruit in a pre-tarred steel mesh fully immersed in a glass container with ethanol. Ethanol instead of water was used to avoid the tendency of water to invade the air spaces when the fruit is immersed.

The fresh weight of the fruit was determined gravimetrically and weight loss was expressed as the percentage of the initial weight.

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*Statistical
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173 One-way ANOVA and correlational analyses were performed using SPSS ver. 19.0. The multicomparison
174 of means was assessed by Tukey's test at a significance level of 0.05. The main effects of CO₂ treatment,
175 storage time and the treatment/time interactions on strawberry fruit were analysed. The data
176 corresponding to the fruit at harvest and the strawberries exposed to the different treatments were
177 analyzed by analysis of variance (ANOVA) and a principal component analysis (PCA).

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179 **Results and Discussion**

180 *Water status*

181 **The unfreezable (bound) water** content was assessed in strawberries stored at 0 °C for 3 days with 0, 20 or
182 40 % CO₂, and after exposure to air for one day (Fig. 1). In all readings oxygen concentration was kept at
183 20 %. These changes were compared with those observed in fruit at harvest. There was a significant
184 depletion in the bound water content (65 %) in 40 % CO₂-treated fruit at the end of treatment with respect
185 to the values in freshly harvested strawberries. The decrease in the amount of bound water in 40 % CO₂-
186 treated fruit reverted after transfer to air for 1 day. Since the total water content did not decrease (Fig.1 40
187 % CO₂ vs 40 % CO₂+1day air), it is clear that the conversion of free water to bound water can be assumed
188 in fruit recovering from excessive high CO₂ treatment. There was also less bound water in strawberries
189 stored at 0 °C with no CO₂ supplementation (0 % CO₂). Furthermore, in these fruits the lowest total water
190 content was quantified (Fig. 1). **Our results indicate that storage at low temperature storage without CO₂ (0**
191 **%) or excessively high CO₂ (40 %), produced a drop in the bound water fraction content.** On the contrary,
192 in 20 % CO₂-treated strawberries the increase in the amount of bound water fraction was evident at the end
193 of treatment and even more after transfer to air. **Changes in bound water content caused by different**
194 **environmental factors have been observed in different plants (Yoshida et al. 1997; Gusta et al. 2004) and**
195 **in different tissues of harvested table grape clusters (Goñi et al. 2011). In view of the above results it is**
196 **reasonable to ask if the changes in water status could be a signal that induces metabolic responses in fruit**
197 **during storage, in line with that suggested by Passioura and Munns (2000) for leaves, or for the onset of the**
198 **ripening process in fruit as suggested by Frenkel and Hartman (2012).**

199 *Simple sugars and polyols*

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201 In order to identify the causes of the variations in the aforementioned water fractions, we analyzed the
202 changes in sugars (sucrose, glucose and fructose) and their polyol derivatives in strawberries stored at 0
203 °C with 0, 20 or 40 % CO₂, keeping a 20 % O₂ concentration in each of them (Table 1). The content of
204 sugars and polyols was assessed in strawberries at the end of the 3-day treatments and after transfer to air
205 for one day. The sucrose concentration was lowest in strawberries stored without added CO₂, reaching
206 values of 13.8 mg/g FW, 25 % lower than in freshly harvested fruit (control fruit). In these fruits, the
207 decrease in fructose (-39 %) or glucose (-31 %) were the highest changes detected. A marked decrease in
208 glucose and fructose was also quantified in strawberries treated with 40 % CO₂. Apart from acting as energy
209 sources and osmoregulators, sugars serve as hydroxyl scavengers in response to oxidative stress and in
210 stabilizing membranes, as well as fulfilling other versatile functions (Couée et al. 2006). Moreover, for
211 glucose and fructose they serve as a substrate for sorbitol and mannitol, respectively. Compared to reducing
212 sugars, these sugar alcohols are chemically less reactive. The maximum absolute value detected for these
213 polyols was significantly lower than the levels of *myo*-inositol that reached values of 581.9 µg/g FW at
214 harvest (Table 1). From this initial level there was a significant decrease in fruit stored without added CO₂
215 (43 %), which was milder in 40 % CO₂-treated fruit (34 %) and only 8 % in the case of 20 % CO₂-treated
216 fruit. The amount of *myo*-inositol quantified in fruit treated with 40 % CO₂ significantly increased after
217 transfer to air, during the recovery from damage induced by excessively high CO₂ levels. Our data are
218 consistent with a model in which the possible protection afforded by this cyclitol may protect the fruit from
219 severe storage conditions. Moreover, *myo*-inositol plays important structural and signaling roles in animal
220 and plant cells and in the environment (Irvine, 2005), being involved in the phosphate cycle of terrestrial
221 and freshwater ecosystems (Turner et al. 2002). The amount of free *myo*-inositol detected here was
222 significantly higher than that quantified in *Fragaria x ananassa* cv. Camarosa (Bodelón et al. 2010) or from
223 *Fragaria vesca* from the first inflorescence (Blanch et al. 2012). Moreover, when comparing carbohydrates
224 during Camarosa growth under two geoclimatic conditions, no significant differences were reported in the
225 soluble carbohydrate at the two locations, except for inositol (Macías- Rodríguez et al. 2002). From the
226 above, it would seem that interaction with the environment has a direct influence on *myo*-inositol levels.
227 Moreover, the ability of this fruit to maintain high levels of *myo*-inositol is consistent with a possible
228 protection afforded by this cyclitol. The presence of sorbitol and/or mannitol follows a strong taxonomical
229 and ecotypic pattern, sorbitol being a major constituent of the leaves and
230 fruit of many species from families such as *Rosaceae* (Gao et al. 2003). In Mara des Bois, the sorbitol

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231 content (35.79 µg/g FW) did not change markedly in the different storage conditions compared to the
232 content in fruit at harvest, with the highest content found in 20 % CO₂-treated fruit (+15 %). The low
233 quantities of mannitol (1.8 µg/g FW) only increased in fruit stored without added CO₂, suggesting that
234 interconversion of fructose in mannitol is, to a certain extent, modulated under severe low temperature
235 storage. Polyol accumulation has been correlated with osmoprotection, serving as a reserve carbon
236 source, as well as promoting protection against salt and photooxidative stress (Williamson et al. 2002;
237 Merchant and Richter 2011) however their mechanistic role in fresh fruit remains unclear.

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239 *The thermodynamic parameters of polyols*

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content of 25.79 g/g FW) did not change markedly by the different storage conditions compared to the
hydroxyl groups and, as, in the highest content of the in 20%, sorbitol and mannitol (5.6) chemically
reduced forms of mannitol (1.81 g/g FW) in cryo, created perfractans, and with the addition of CO₂, suggesting that
interpolyols. When the test of mannitol is set (H₂O) increases from calculated solution of Dewber (a) and
strange (P) and *myo*-inositol (S) been correlated with its concentration (weight fraction reserve: Fig. 2),
slide of the walls, disrupting a direct dependence and a high correlation in this figure (with this data (acc 2002g
Murahat, 2008) over 2011) in order to investigate the mechanism of water in the solution (Fig. 2). *Myo*-inositol reached
values of 9.1 mol H₂O/mol solute, higher than that of sorbitol and mannitol with values of 5.2 and 5.4 mol
H₂O/mol solute, indicating that much more unfrozen water can accumulate in aqueous solutions of *myo*-
inositol. Furthermore, PCA analysis (Fig. 3), performed on the autoscaled data (6 strawberry treatments and
10 variables) and that accounted for 84.29 % of the total variance, showed a clear separation between *myo*-
inositol and the other polyols in relation to bound water. So, while *myo*-inositol was located in the positive
part of PC1 joined to simple sugars, the third group composed of sorbitol was found in PC3 and no addition
for mannitol. *Myo*-inositol has unique biochemical properties (Loewus and Murthy 2000). Regarding the
effect of polyols on water structuring Politi et al (2009) reported differences between *myo*-inositol and
sorbitol despite having the same number of hydroxyl groups so, *myo*-inositol forms no internal hydrogen
bonds and creates more interpolyol bonds than sorbitol. According to these authors in the context that
water
ordering decreases in the presence of polyols (Dipaola and Belleau 1977), these compounds may disrupt

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261 the surrounding water molecules, thereby restricting the ability of water to adopt a perfect network
262 structure, and this could influence the maintenance of the cell integrity at aqueous interfaces. A water
263 vapour absorption mechanism in arthropods by accumulation of *myo*-inositol and glucose has been
264 reported by Bayley and Holstrump (1999). These authors also indicated that this type of water vapour
265 absorption confers the capability of meeting the water requirements of a terrestrial arthropod under
266 prolonged drought stress. In spite of the high water binding capacity of *myo*-inositol, it was clearly lower
267 than that of the short-chain FOS (Blanch et al. 2012) but higher than that of sucrose (Furuki 2002 and
268 references therein). **Considering the above thermodynamic properties of *myo*-inositol and FOS, we suggest**
269 **consider that fruit storability and preparedness for environmental change may be reflected in the**
270 **accumulation of these carbohydrates at harvest.**

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272 *Short-chain FOS (3-5 sugar moieties)*

273 The profiles of FOS with less than five units were generated from strawberries at the end of treatment with
274 0, 20 or 40 % CO₂ and after exposure to air for one day. 1-kestose [1^F-(1-β-D- fructofuranosyl)sucrose],
275 nystose [6^G (1-β-D-fructofuranosyl)₂ sucrose] and kestopentaose [1^F-(1-β-D- fructofuranosyl)₃ sucrose]
276 were identified and quantified by HPAEC-PAD (Table 2). 1-kestose constitutes the main FOS, reaching
277 values of 84.6 µg/g FW in freshly harvested fruit, 17 times that found for nystose, the next most abundant
278 FOS. Whereas no significant differences were observed in 20 % CO₂- treated fruit with respect to fruit at
279 harvest, the amount of 1-kestose markedly decreased in fruit stored without added CO₂ and in 40 % CO₂-
280 treated fruit, reaching values of 51.8 and 45.4 µg/g FW, respectively. Interestingly, the levels of 1-kestose
281 in 40 % CO₂-treated fruit were restored after exposure to air, with an increase in 1-kestose of 53 %. The
282 fructose/1-kestose and sucrose/1-kestose ratio also changed after transfer to air, suggesting that **conversion**
283 **of sucrose to FOS** did seem to occur during the recovery from excessively high CO₂ levels. Apart from the
284 well-known health benefits for human, there are many positive aspects related to the presence of fructans
285 in plants (Livingston et al. 2009; McIntyre et al. 2012; Dominguez et al. 2014). They provide protection
286 from the damage caused to cytosolic proteins and cell membranes by severe low temperature (Hoekstra et
287 al. 2001). Indeed, it has been reported that fructans can interact strongly with cell membranes through direct
288 hydrogen bonding with phosphatidylcholine lipid bilayers (Hincha et al. 2000; Vereyken et al. 2001). A
289 previous DSC analysis
290 revealed that 1-kestose, nystose and kestopentaose, exhibit a very high water-binding capacity, with

291 values of 17.5, 18.9 and 29 mol H₂O/mol solute, respectively (Blanch et al. 2012). Furthermore, the
292 aforementioned PCA (Fig.3) showed that FOS (nystose and 1-kestose) and bound water content are more
293 closely related and they were located in the positive part of PC2. It is reasonable to assume that hydrogen
294 bonds created between water molecules in close proximity to FOS could contribute to the increase in
295 bound water fraction.

297 *Cellular integrity, air space content and weight loss*

298 The LT-SEM micrographs of fractured tissues (Fig. 4) revealed an excess of a surrounding aqueous solution
299 in tissues treated with 40 % CO₂ in part linked to wall disassembly and degradation (Fig. 4D). However,
300 this excess aqueous solution in tissues treated with 40 % CO₂ partially disappeared after exposure to air
301 (Fig. 4E). Translucency is a physiological disorder of unknown cause that occurs when the cell-free spaces
302 become full of liquid, damaging the tissues and giving them a transparent or crystalline aspect. In melon,
303 translucency is diminished by the use of environments rich in CO₂ (15 kPa) (Portella and Cantwell 1998).
304 In micrographs of strawberries treated with 20 % CO₂, empty intercellular gas spaces and a well defined
305 cellular structure was evident at the end of the treatment (Fig. 4B). The structural characteristics visualized
306 were confirmed by our observation that whole fruit treated with 20 % CO₂ exhibited a significantly higher
307 proportion of air space than those exposed to 40 % CO₂ (Fig. 4, inset 1). In fact, fruit treated with 20% CO₂
308 exhibited the highest proportion of air space at the end of the 3 days of treatment. The connection between
309 the significantly greater percentage air space in fruit exposed to 20 % CO₂ treatment may have functional
310 implications on gaseous diffusion, although this has yet to be determined. It has been stated that an increase
311 in the air space in fruit is expected to lead to easier cell separation and a change in texture (Hatfield and
312 Knee, 1988). It is well known that cell separation, which permits spatial displacement of two adjacent cells,
313 is an important event for fruit softening (Roy et al., 1997). Interestingly, our data showed that air space
314 percentage observed in 20 % CO₂-treated fruit reverted after transfer to air and that this percentage did not
315 increase by increasing the concentration of CO₂. Furthermore, LT-SEM imaging confirmed this increase in
316 air space, specifically, in 20 % CO₂- treated fruit. Treatment with 40 % CO₂ was associated with the lowest
317 rate of weight loss assessed by measuring the weight reduction over the 3-day period (Fig. 4, inset 1). Our
318 data indicate that the reported decrease in bound water content in 40 % CO₂-treated fruit, in part due to the
319 conversion of bound to free
320 water, could in turn pull water from adjacent cells, thereby generating extra water in the extracellular

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2 321 spaces that restrains water loss in these fruits. In accordance with this, Wardlaw (2005) suggested that
322 apoplastic water should not be ignored in plant water studies.

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6 324 **Conclusions**

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8 325 **The degree of tolerance to severe storage conditions in Mara des Bois strawberries (*Fragaria vesca*) is**
9
10 326 **associated with marked changes in water status, connected with the availability of reserve carbohydrates.**

11
12 327 **Our results show that the decrease in bound water is linked to stress and consequently the re-**
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14 328 **establishment of initial levels is associated with the ability to recover from unfavourable high CO₂ levels.**

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16 329 Evidence for the preferential protection afforded by storage plus 20 % CO₂ was obtained by demonstrating
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18 330 a predominant accumulation of bound water and carbohydrates, with a special emphasis on 1-kestose and
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20 331 *myo*-inositol, in such fruit. The ability of these compounds to reorganize water-hydrogen bonding networks
21
22 332 might be the key factor involved in the stabilization of macromolecule aqueous interfaces. These CO₂-
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24 333 driven changes in water status would allow fruit to retain water in the cell more efficiently. Such a beneficial
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26 334 effect is probably more important in the case of strawberries, because these fruit tissues can be easily
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28 335 damaged due to a lack of external protection and softness.

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39 340 889/2008.

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59 **437 Figure captions**

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438 Fig.1. Changes in the content of unfreezable (bound) water fraction (g/g dry weight) and in the total water
439 content (g/g dry weight) in strawberries at harvest (control), after 3 days of storage at 0 °C in 0 %, 20 %
440 or 40 % CO₂ and one day after exposure to air. Dark bars indicate bound water content. The data are
441 presented as the mean ± SE of three replicates (n = 6), and the letters indicate significant differences ($P <$
442 0.05).

443 Fig.2. Relationship between heat of fusion of ice, H_f and the rate of increase in the concentration of D-
444 sorbitol (A), D-mannitol (B) or *myo*-inositol (C), with a correlation coefficient as high as 0.99, for each
445 polyol studied.

446 Fig.3. Three-dimensional diagram of the principal component analysis (PCA) of 6 strawberry treatments
447 and 10 variables. Percentages of the first 3 principal components (PC1: 37.24; PC2: 24.62 and PC3: 22.44)
448 explained 84.29 % of the total variability.

449 Fig. 4. LTSEM micrographs showing cells of fractured Mara des Bois strawberries after 3 days of storage
450 at 0 °C in 0 % CO₂ (A), in 20 % CO₂ (B), and one day after transfer to air (C), or in 40 % CO₂ (D) and one
451 day after transfer to air (E). The extracellular space is indicated by double arrows and the scale bars
452 represent 200 µm. Inset 1 shows the changes in air space and weight loss percentages of strawberries stored
453 under the different treatments. The data are presented as the mean ± SE of three replicates (n = 6), and the
454 letters indicate significant differences ($P < 0.05$).

Fig.1

weight fraction, wt, %

Fig. 4

① Treatments	Air space (%)	Weight loss (%)
0% CO ₂	3.48±1.68a	0.3631±0.09b
20% CO ₂	7.63±1.25b	0.3395±0.04ab
20% CO ₂ +1d air	2.72±0.75a	0.3350±0.02ab
40% CO ₂	2.32±1.15a	0.2722±0.07a
40% CO ₂ +1d air	2.54±0.81a	0.3312±0.05ab

Fig. 3

	Component		
	1	2	3
myo-Inositol (inosit)	.917	-.109	.180
Fructose (frut)	.835	.427	.247
Glucose (glu)	.829	.247	.409
Sucrose (suc)	.718	.147	.143
Mannitol (manit)	-.641	-.359	.591
Nystose (nyst)		.935	-.204
UFW (bound water)	.215	.835	.424
Kestose (kest)	.613	.686	.168
Sorbitol (sorbit)	.240		.828
Kestopentaose (kestop)	-.306	-.107	-.824

Extraction Method: Principal Component Analysis.

Rotation Method: Varimax with Kaiser Normalization.

Table 1: Sugars (mg/g FW) and polyols ($\mu\text{g/g}$ FW) in strawberries *Fragaria vesca* cv. Mara des Bois at harvest, 3 days of storage at 0 °C with 0, 20 % or 40 % CO₂ and after exposure to air for 1 day. In all readings oxygen concentration was kept at 20 %.

	At harvest	Treatments				
	Control	0 % CO ₂	20 %CO ₂	20 %CO ₂ +1d air	40 % CO ₂	40 % CO ₂ +1d air
Sugars						
glucose (mg/g FW)	27.20±2.2b	18.74±1.7a	25.39±1.2b	22.27±4.5ab	19.36±2.6a	23.56±0.6ab
fructose (mg/g FW)	26.54±2.6c	17.85±1.8a	24.32±1.4c	25.59±1.9c	19.09±3.0ab	23.15±1.2bc
sucrose (mg/g FW)	18.05±0.6ab	13.80±1.2a	19.61±2.0b	17.67±1.9ab	16.93±2.6ab	18.35±2.8ab
Polyols						
myo-inositol ($\mu\text{g/g}$ FW)	581.92±34.3d	332.33±17.9a	534.25±39.8cd	436.77±70.0bc	383.89±58.3ab	485.92± 12.2c
sorbitol ($\mu\text{g/g}$ FW)	35.79±2.15b	33.89±0.9ab	42.29±1.2c	32.57±0.8ab	29.67±2.7a	31.97±1.6ab
mannitol ($\mu\text{g/g}$ FW)	1.85±0.2b	2.90±1.1c	2.07±0.4b	1.27±0.1a	1.41±0.2a	2.11±0.1b

Data are presented as the means SE of three replicates (n = 6) and the different letters within rows indicate significant differences at $P < 0.05$.

Table 2: Fructo-oligosaccharides ($\mu\text{g/g}$ FW) in strawberries *Fragaria vesca* cv. Mara de Bois at harvest, 3 days of storage at 0 °C with 0, 20 % or 40 % CO₂ and after exposure to air for 1 day. In all readings oxygen concentration was kept at 20 %.

	At harvest	Treatments				
	Control	0%CO ₂	20%CO ₂	20%CO ₂ +1d air	40% CO ₂	20%CO ₂ +1d air
<i>FOS</i>						
1-Kestose	84.65±1.4b	51.88±4.7a	79.27±2.9b	85.98±3.4b	45.40±0.5a	79.44±5.16b
Nystose	4.82±0.1c	4.43±0.5c	5.02±0.2c	11.05±0.6d	3.50±0.1b	1.29±0.2a
Kestopentaose	1.05±0.1a	2.26±0.5bc	1.15±0.5ab	2.54±0.5c	0.82±0.5a	2.92±0.4c
Fructose/1-kestose	0.31	0.34	0.31	0.30	0.42	0.29
Sucrose/1-kestose	0.21	0.26	0.25	0.20	0.38	0.23

Data are presented as the means SE of three replicates (n = 6) and the different letters within rows indicate significant differences at $P < 0.05$.

It has been recognized that beneficial high CO₂ delays wilting and reduces weight loss in harvested plant products. Since strawberry fruits have high tolerance thresholds to CO₂, it is of interest to know what changes occur in fruit water status when these thresholds are reached and exceeded. Changes in the content of unfreezable (bound) water were analysed in relation to the simple sugars, polyols and fructooligosaccharides (FOS) in strawberries (*Fragaria vesca* L. Mara des Bois) stored at severe low temperature (0 °C) with 0, 20 or 40 % CO₂. The relationship between cellular water status and these compounds was analyzed at the end of a 3 day treatments and after exposure to air for one day. Unfavourable storage conditions were associated with a significant decrease in the levels of bound water, and in simple sugars, 1-kestose and *myo*-inositol. The 1-kestose and *myo*-inositol content was enhanced when fruit treated with excessive high CO₂ (40 %) were exposure to air at the same time as there was a marked increase in bound water content and a restoration of intracellular water. The ability of fruit to modulate the accumulation of these compounds, and by extension the water binding strength, in conjunction with the pool of the bound water fraction, appears to be an important mechanism to avoid damage. Variations in the percentages of air space and weight loss produced by enhancing the CO₂ treatments during storage at 0 °C were also analyzed.